

AN ATOMISTIC STUDY OF CREEP BEHAVIOR IN FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE

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INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite has been increasingly used in civil engineering field. The durability of CFRP composite is highly dependent on the interfacial integrity between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix. During the long-term service-life, the composite is inevitably subject to external loads, which causes the creep between fiber and matrix. As interfacial creep occurs, especially under the severe load, it leads to the variation in the local interfacial region, which affects the CFRP composite durability. However, it is still not clear about how the microstructure of fiber/matrix interface changes during the creep, which impedes a complete understanding of the interfacial deterioration in CFRP composite.

OBJECTIVES

This study aims to investigate the microscopic creep behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy interface at different load levels using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, to understand more in-depth about the variation in the interfacial structure and properties during the creep process, and to obtain a fundamental understanding of the interfacial deterioration in CFRP, so as to predict the creep behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy interface in consideration of the environmental exposure during the long-term service-life.

CREEP RESPONSE

Displacement as a function of force

- A threshold load exists before the total interfacial detachment, which is in the range of 1000 pN and 1100 pN corresponding to 32.03 MPa and 35.23 MPa, respectively.
- The threshold stress agree very well with the previous simulated interfacial stress of 34.4 ± 1.4 MPa, while it is slightly higher than the experimental interfacial stress of 19.9 ± 8.1 MPa.

MODELING AND SIMULATION

INTERFACIAL BEHAVIOR

Strain as a function of time

- In the low stress levels regime, the strain increases slightly at the first stage (stage I), and then the increasing rate of the strain starts to decrease at the second stage (stage II), and finally reaches a constant value and no interfacial detachment is observed.
- In the high stress regime, after the similar first two stages, the final detachment between the graphite sheets and the epoxy occurs due to the significant accelerated sliding of graphite sheets during the second stage.
- It is believed that the strategy developed in this study is applicable to the simulation of the larger-scale interface model for investigating the effect of fiber surface treatments, structural defects, and environmental exposure on the interfacial creep behavior.

After equilibration

Stage I

Stage II

Detachment

CONCLUSIONS

- It is found that the creep response of the interface exhibits two distinct regimes under different load levels, and the threshold stress is found.
- The simulation results demonstrate the molecular changes of fiber/matrix interface during the creep process under different load levels.
- This study provides nanoscale insights into the creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface, which contributes to the understanding of interfacial integrity of CFRP composite.

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